

RAMONES

Radioactivity Monitoring in Ocean Ecosystems

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Disclaimer

RAMONES is a European Innovation Council (EIC) FET Proactive project in the Environmental Intelligence Scope B, related to radically novel approaches to resilient, reliable and environmentally responsible in-situ monitoring, funded by European Union under Horizon 2020 FET proactive programme, via grant agreement No. 101017808.

RAMONES project's main objective is to close the current marine radioactivity under-sampling gap and foster new interdisciplinary research in ocean ecosystems. RAMONES will invest a significant effort to provide tools to enable long-term data acquisition missions, rapid deployments, low cost per information byte, and propose new AI and Robotics-driven and supported methodologies, being ambitious to eventually offer scaled-up solutions to researchers, policy makers and communities. All these may be achieved by combining state-of-the-art (SoA) methodologies and equipment from various disciplines in a well-balanced synergy, and designing new and effective methodologies targeting the marine environment, which will provide efficient response to existing natural and man-made hazards, and shape future policies for the global population. RAMONES will additionally contribute to shaping a blueprint on Environmental Intelligence in the EU and worldwide.

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Abstract

The dedicated website for RAMONES will be one of the most important channels to promote the dissemination and communication of the performed work, results, and impact of the ongoing activities of the project. The website is designed at the beginning of the activities and will be updated frequently throughout the whole life of the project, including updated information concerning the project and the consortium, news, achievements, events, downloadable material and any relevant contents of interest.

The RAMONES site is available online and can be accessed at **www.ramones-project.eu**. The website has been designed considering the alignment to the defined visual identity and includes the main recommendations for the best user experience, considering accessibility, web browsing facilities, security or content organization.

The RAMONES site is expected to attract both individual visitors and stakeholders with an interest in Underwater activities, Radioactivity, Ecosystems, Natural and Man-made hazards, Marine engineering or ICT fields, and will constitute an important source of information for them, including contents for expert and non-expert audiences.

The contents will be available in the most appropriate format (formatted text, brochures, whitepapers, news, reports, multimedia, links, etc) according to the scope and the envisioned targets. Academic and technical audiences (such as scientific communities, research centers, developers, or public institutions) will have the opportunity to benefit from the material published, as well as stakeholders of other European projects in order to identify synergies and potential lines of collaboration. Journalists will find updated information such as news, events or press releases and will be able to additionally subscribe to RSS streams. In order to boost these media, the website also includes a direct link to social media platforms, such as Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, Instagram and YouTube. These platforms offer an efficient way to publicize the RAMONES project and increase its recognition in the scientific community, as well as to approach a broader audience and public communities. This audience, outside the scientific community, are people across borders belonging to age, gender, and/or social groups with limited access to conferences and science fairs. The ergonomic exploitation of the social media platforms is the main RAMONES social media strategy.

In addition to the above, the RAMONES consortium and other interested and supporting stakeholders can use their own communication channels to ensure a wider dissemination and promotion of the RAMONES project among their ranks and collaborative networks. RAMONES will provide links and material to facilitate this dissemination. The website will be linked from and to the partners' website and relevant scientific communities.

The document presents the management model (both from a technical and contents perspective) and the tracking of impact and use, followed by the definition of a functional model as a preliminary step to the development, illustrated in the final part of the document with a large number of screenshots together with explanations and relevant comments.

1. Introduction

1.1 Context

This document corresponds to the 1st deliverable of WP5, “Citizen Awareness, Dissemination and Communication Activities” with its objectives being the following:

- to establish a visual and textually recognizable impression of the project and its work.
- to maximize the visibility and impact of the project works and achievements.
- to engage stakeholders that can support sustainability of the project via both update and feedback provisioning and can further empower the vision around Open Science.
- to provide essential information and knowledge on the RAMONES project to 3rd parties activating especially in H2020 projects, thematic communities, Open Science and FAIR Ecosystem.

A dedicated website for the RAMONES project is one of the most important channels to promote the dissemination and communication of the performed work, results, and impact of the ongoing activities of this project. The website is designed at the beginning of the activities and will be updated throughout the whole life of the project (planned cycle: weekly), including updated information concerning the project implementation and the consortium, news, achievements, events, downloadable material and any relevant content of interest.

1.2 Objective and approval

This document concerns an integrated presentation of the design of the website, based on a web content management system in order to allow dynamic addition of content as well as linking to project services for access by stakeholders. Its contents can consider a business, functional and technical perspective, according to the different target audience.

The project website is developed in line with the visual identity that has been developed for the project. Maximum visibility of the website is ensured by:

- Engaging design and user-friendly navigation.
- Information relevant to each communication target, easy to find and clearly identified (e.g. underwater, radioactivity, ecosystems, natural and man-made hazards, marine engineering and robotics, core services, forecasting and risk management).
- Search Engine Optimization: relevant keywords and external links to the website on local pages and partner projects. Meta content will be quietly incorporated in the website to facilitate search crawlers to archive the relevant keywords.
- A smart city community page will cross-link to and from other smart city projects as well as the EIP (European Innovation Partnership) marketplace.
- Interactive content: videos and blog updates (targeted update frequency: monthly) will keep the website active and relevant during the lifespan of the project.

The website has been designed considering the alignment to the defined visual identity and includes the main recommendations for the best user experience, considering accessibility, web browsing facilities, security or content organization.

RAMONES site is available online and can be accessed at www.ramones-project.eu.

2. Website Aims and Objectives

2.1 Purpose

The website is the primary information source for several RAMONES project target groups. As a primary communication tool, the website address will be featured in all project's communication material.

The purpose of the website is to proactively promote the project and its final results by providing targeted information to various audiences within and beyond the project's own community. The specific goals of this dissemination and communication channel are the following:

- To be a reference point of knowledge about the project, including the scope and the framework, the consortium, the project organization and the activities.
- To be a content hub updated with the main reports, documents, and any produced material concerning RAMONES.
- To be a reference point for dissemination and engagement, both with its own content and through connections to other sites or platforms.

2.2 Target audience

The RAMONES site is expected to attract both individual visitors and stakeholders with an interest in Underwater, Radioactivity, Ecosystems, Natural and Man-made hazards, Marine engineering, Risk Management and Forecasting or ICT fields, and will constitute an important source of information for them, including contents for expert and non-expert audiences.

Academic and technical audiences (such as scientific communities, research centers, developers, or public institutions) will have the opportunity to benefit from the material published, as well as other European projects in order to identify synergies and potential lines of collaboration. Journalists will find updated information, such as news, events or press releases.

2.3 Project knowledge

The goal is to display and promote the knowledge of the project, on a wide range of topics, but particularly the research and technology communities (focusing underwater, on radioactivity and ecosystems monitoring, natural and man-made hazards resulting from radioactivity, marine engineering/robotics technology, Risk Management and Forecasting and ICT field) in the European scope including the H2020 program.

2.4 Content hub

The website operates as a repository for a wide type of information and communication material. The contents will be available in the most appropriate format (formatted text, leaflets, brochures, whitepapers, news, reports, multimedia, links, ...) according to the scope and the target.

2.5 Dissemination and networking

The website includes a link to social media platforms (Facebook, Twitter, Linked In, Instagram and YouTube). The RAMONES Consortium and other interested and supporting stakeholders

can use their own communication channels to ensure a wider dissemination and promotion of the RAMONES project among their ranks and collaborative networks. RAMONES will provide links to facilitate this dissemination. The website will be linked from and to the partners' website and relevant scientific communities.

3. Management model

3.1 Technical management

The site is based on a web content management system. The infrastructure and hosting services are provided by NKUA in cooperation with IST-ID and the whole project consortium, facilitating a whole management of the entire platform in the scope of RAMONES.

The technical management includes not only the servers, but also the definition of back-up policies, operation, maintenance and security issues. Full daily backups have been configured and, in case of failure, a recovery procedure is defined to recover the site as soon as possible.

At its first stage, all the site structure has been designed by an experts' group skilled in website development (site map, menus, browsing facilities, embedded tools, etc.) according to the functional definition of the web in close collaboration with the RAMONES team. This structure can be reviewed and updated according to new business or technical needs.

During maintenance works, a restricted access (by means of user and password) can be presented.

3.2 Content management

The website contents are handled by the *content manager*, who is responsible for keeping the site updated. This role can be played by more than one person in order to facilitate the management for the whole life of the project. This role is performed by means of a specific Content Manager profile in order to avoid their access to structural changes and protect the site against inconvenient actions.

Loading of content can be managed / validated by the technical leaders at 1st level, by the dissemination leader at 2nd level and lastly by the Project Manager at 3rd level, depending on the type of content.

All content has to comply with the good practices and style books about European recommendations and ethics.

3.3 Schedule and impact tracking

The web page will be regularly updated. Moreover, the effectiveness of the web page will be periodically analysed by means of the Google Analytics tool. This will allow reports to be run on the website, giving a very clear picture of information such as:

- Users count visiting the website and visit time.
- Languages and locations of visitors.
- Devices used for browsing the website.

4. Functional model

This section describes the functionality of the website according to the structure presented above.

4.1 Accessing and presentation

The website, as stated above, is hosted in the following domain: www.ramones-project.eu

The approach is to offer all the facilities to allow the identification of RAMONES, and an easy browsing experience. This goal will be achieved through the following actions:

- Use of RAMONES logos and the defined look & feel all around the site.
- Well-structured menus architecture, split in two sections: Top head menu concerning standard browsing and tools, and Main menu with the specific information about the project itself.
- Definition of clear and organized site, without unneeded or “heavy” content.
- Mobile oriented, considering responsive features for smartphone and tablet.
- Quick access to Home page at any time, by means of Home menu and the RAMONES logo.
- The site can support formatted text, images, video playback, file hosting, and URL services.

4.2 Structure

The web site is made up of different parts: browsing management area and content area. The browsing management area consists of 2 menus to handle the navigation of the website, whilst the content is the main area to display the contents.

The organization of the presentation is the following:

- **Top Head Menu**, presented in a horizontal bar, with key functionalities for site handling, information about the project, news and social network icons.
- **Main Menu**, presented in a horizontal bar, concerning the logo, the project contents and the “get in touch” icon.
- **Content area**, including the introductory field (header image or video) at the top and the relevant content presented as a text, images, lists of links that can be the starting point to other pages and other sections of interest.
- **Footer**, always present at the bottom with the project’s contact information, the leading hashtags of the project, the social network icons, the head menu list for quick access, a reference to the European H2020 Grant Agreement, as well as the Disclaimer and Cookie Policy.

The basic structure of the website design is illustrated in the following figure:

Figure 1. Website structure

4.3 Top Head Menu

The menu bar is always available at the top of the site with the options described below:

- Item 1

Menu Topic	Home
Description	This option is a direct link to the Home page.
Type of action	Home page is presented with all its menus.
Dependent Submenus	None

- Item 2

Menu Topic	About
Description	Specific information about the project RAMONES. In the Content area a short description and the aims of the project are displayed.
Type of action	The Content Area remains the same.
Dependent Submenus	None

- Item 3

Menu Topic	Advisory board
Description	Reference by name of the members of the Advisory board of the project.
Type of action	The Content Area remains the same.
Dependent Submenus	None

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● Item 4

Menu Topic	Consortium
Description	<p>Presentation of all the project members by means of their logo in the Content area.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">When selecting any logo, the Content Area is updated with the link to the partner web site. Clicking the link, a new tab is opened in the Browser with the partner home page.
Type of action	The Content Area remains the same.
Dependent Submenus	None

● Item 5

Menu Topic	News
Description	<p>News is structured according to different thematic categories. These categories constitute the Blog categories which can be expanded in the future to include additional subjects and thematics relevant to the project objectives. Taking advantage of the built-in dynamic presentation of the contents, news will be updated on a regular basis. By selecting this tab, a list of news will appear in the Content area which is organized by date. The most recent news entries are presented as a headline in the sidebar at the right part of the Content area. Each news item can be selected in case the user wants extended information; in this case, the information occupies the full Content area. Every news item will be labeled by relevant keywords and a Tags tool in the Content area will be updated automatically. Finally, In the content area a Search engine helps the user to find any required content (in case of no results, a message is displayed otherwise a list is displayed in the Content area).</p>
Type of action	Content Area is cleared and updated with corresponding contents.
Dependent Submenus	<ul style="list-style-type: none">HomeCategory

● Item 6

Menu Topic	Synergies
Description	<p>Joint activities with other projects and affiliated projects are presented in the Content area. This area is divided horizontally in two sections. The one concerning Joint Activities with EnvIntel FET projects and the other one the Affiliated to RAMONES Projects</p>
Type of action	Content Area is cleared and updated with corresponding contents.
Dependent Submenus	None

- Item 7

Menu Topic	Social Networks
Description	Connection to the RAMONES social network accounts: Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, LinkedIn and YouTube. The connection is made by, according to UX decision, directly through the logo of each network displayed in the main page and at the end of any article/news.
Type of action	After selecting any social network, a new tab is opened in the browser with the access to its home page. The Content Area remains the same.
Dependent Submenus	None.

4.4 Main Menu

The menu bar is always available at the top of the site with the options described below:

- Item 1

Menu Topic	Logo (icon)
Description	Same as Home in the top menu.
Type of action	Same as Home in the top menu.
Dependent Submenus	None.

- Item 2

Menu Topic	The Approach
Description	The scope of the project RAMONES is described in the Content area.
Type of action	The Content Area remains the same.
Dependent Submenus	None.

- Item 3

Menu Topic	Environmental Intelligence
Description	Selecting this option, a description of the collaboration of the project RAMONES with other H2020 pathfinder projects for achieving Environmental Intelligence will appear in the Content Area.
Type of action	The Content Area remains the same.
Dependent Submenus	None.

- Item 4

Menu Topic	Training
Description	In this topic, information about webinars, summer schools, hands-on practical training and internships are presented and will be updated.
Type of action	Content Area is cleared and updated with corresponding contents.
Dependent Submenus	None.

- Item 5

Menu Topic	Events
Description	Presentation of main events, trade and science fairs, congresses, conferences, workshops etc. in which the project is/has been involved. The list includes both the events already held and the ones to come. A list is displayed in the Content Area, by the same functionality as the News tab.
Type of action	Content Area is cleared and updated with corresponding contents.
Dependent Submenus	None.

- Item 6

Menu Topic	Publications
Description	Presentation of journal papers, conference papers, public reports, dissemination articles such as blueprints for environmental intelligence, press articles, long abstracts, public data sets (FAIR, OA), conference posters, talks, etc in which the project is/has been involved. A list is displayed in the Content Area, by the same functionality as the News tab.
Type of action	Content Area is cleared and updated with corresponding contents.
Dependent Submenus	None.

- Item 7

Menu Topic	Get in touch
Description	User's data can be filled up in the available contact form contact for together with a message or report about any technical issue. This form is connected with the official e-mail address of RAMONES.
Type of action	The Content Area remains the same.
Dependent Submenus	None.

4.5 Content area

This area of the site is the main section to display any required content, as it has been described in the menu. At the top is the Header image or video which is also accompanied by the title of each corresponding page. The remaining part of the Content area displays

formatted text, media resources and links to other pages. The page is built using a responsive theme. The Content area is dynamically adjusted to offer optimal presentation functionality.

At Home page the Content area displays:

- RAMONES Highlights (News, Events, Environmental Intelligence)
- RAMONES Objectives (Radioactivity in ocean ecosystems, marine robotics, artificial intelligence, Environmental modelling, Policy making, Fair/OA data)
- Our Consortium (project members by means of their logo)
- A subscription section to the RAMONES Newsletter

4.6 Footer

The Footer bar is always available at the bottom of the site. The contents include the contact information of the Project RAMONES, such as the phone number, official email address and the location. This section also contains the social network accounts of the project, hashtags and the head menu for quick access. An additional link to the RSS feed of the site is included. Moreover, at the bottom of the footer there is a special mention to the European H2020 Programme and Grant Agreement, as well as the Disclaimer, as mentioned on page 4 of the given Deliverable and Cookie Policy.

5. Web site project

This section presents and displays the developed pages of RAMONES site in detail.

The header (top part of the site) contains two parts:

- The top menu, with standard options for browsing and site identification, such as Home, News, About, Advisory Board, News, Synergies and access to RAMONES social networks.
- The RAMONES logo, which is the symbol of the project and an access to the home page and the navigation menu with the options The Approach, Environmental Intelligence, Training, Events, Publications and Get in touch.

In Figure 2 below, the structure of the Top head menu and the Main menu of the header is depicted:

Figure 2. Web site, detail of the Top head and Main menu section

The footer of the page contains three columns, the following functionalities are presented:

- The RAMONES logo with the contact info. It offers a way to access the project managers for any issue concerning the project or the website itself. A specific email address belonging to the project scope (ramones.h2020@gmail.com) has been created and used.

- Direct access to RAMONES social networks.
- Menu list.
- Specific hashtags associated with the project.
- A special mention to European H2020 programme.
- Disclaimer and Cookie Policy

In Figure 3 below, we depict the details of footer section:

Figure 3. Website, detail of footer section

5.1 Top head menu

This section contents all the components regarding the standard practices about the website and user experience.

5.1.1 Home

The home page is the first one that the users find when they access the site. This page can also be reached from the Home menu or from the logo. The Home page consists of an introductory video animation, with a link to the About page (*Find Out More*) and the description of the project, the Highlights, the Objectives, the Consortium and the Subscribe button.

Figure 4. Home page for www.ramones-project.eu

The site is developed using a responsive design to optimize the content delivered and improve the visual experience across various user-end devices, such as PC screen, tablets, or smartphones. What follows is an example of how the website is presented on a smartphone:

Figure 5. Home page from smartphone and example of its responsive design

Scrolling down the highlights of the project are presented. There are three clickable options: News, Events and Environmental Intelligence that lead to a new page. They are also accessible through the header.

Figure 6. Website, the Highlights from Home section

The main objectives of the project (Radioactivity in Ocean Ecosystems, Marine Robotics, Artificial Intelligence, Environmental Modelling, Policy Making, FAIR/OA data) are presented in the following section, with a link to their corresponding page.

RAMONES Objectives

Figure 7. Website, the Objectives from Home section

The Consortium section presents the partners involved in the project (also accessible through header), with a link to a new page including the description of each one of them (see Figure 8).

When clicking on any partner name, the visitor is redirected to a new page containing specific content about the partner (general description, members of the team and links to personal accounts on social media, if any), see Figure 9.

Figure 8. Website, the Consortium from Home section

The National and Kapodistrian University of Athens is one of the major higher degree public educational institutions in Greece. NKUA is the largest state institution of higher learning in Greece, and among the largest universities in Europe and in the top-200 universities in the world (Webometrics, 2021). With a student body of about 125,000 undergraduate and postgraduate students, over 2,000 members of academic staff and approximately 1,800 administrative and secretarial staff and specialized personnel, NKUA aims at excellence in both teaching and research in a significantly varied range of disciplines. NKUA participates in RAMONES with two of Departments of the School of Natural Sciences: (i) Department of Physics and (ii) Department of Geology and Geoenvironment.

The Department of Physics (NKUA-PHYS, www.phys.uoa.gr) is the oldest and highest-ranked department of Physics in Greece. It is among the highest-ranked universities worldwide (rank 101-150 in ARWU Shanghai 2019). The Department has currently 64 faculty members distributed among five (5) Sections (Condensed Matter, Nuclear and Particle, Astrophysics-Astronomy-Mechanics, Environment-Meteorology and Electronics and Systems).

The Department of Geology and Geoenvironment (NKUA-GEOL, <http://www.geol.uoa.gr>) has a declared and established ever growing interest and involvement in basic and applied research concerning contemporary environmental problems and geohazards. It continues to develop and expand by establishing new academic units to accommodate the cascading development of Earth and Earth Observation Sciences.

Figure 9. Website, detail of a partner from the Consortium section of Home page

A Call To Action button for subscription to the RAMONES Newsletter:

Subscribe to the RAMONES Newsletter to be informed on our latest news!

Your Email

Join

Figure 10. Website, the Subscribe area from the Home page

5.1.2 About section

This section contains an executive presentation of the RAMONES project.

RAMONES offers a radical vision of science-enabled cutting-edge solutions in both instrumentation and robotic sensing platforms towards a step change in Radioactivity Monitoring in Ocean Ecosystems.

RAMONES aims **to prove** that innovative combination and advancement of recent developments in sensory materials, low-power autonomous robotic systems, and process modelling theories, have the potential **to overcome current limitations** and open the window to high temporal and spatial resolution underwater radioactivity measurements, in situ and in near real time, forming **a game changer in deep-water environmental monitoring**.

Figure 11. Website, the About section and its content

5.1.3 Advisory Board section

This section presents the members of the Advisory Board of the project.

- Dr Ion Stamatelatos (NCSR "Demokritos" / Nuclear technology and radiation protection)
- Prof. Dr. Christian Hübscher (U. Hamburg / Marine Geophysics)
- Prof. Emer. Dimitrios Papanikolaou (U. Athens / Marine Geohazards)

Figure 12. Website, the Advisory Board section and its content

5.1.4 Consortium section

The Consortium section contains a slider for presenting the partners involved in the project. Each logo is clickable and linked to the home page of the corresponding website.

Figure 13. Website, detail of Consortium page

5.1.5 News section

News section is the area where we can highlight the latest changes and uploaded content to the website. Below is an example of how the News section is presented with a sidebar on the right part of the page for easier navigation to the articles.

Figure 14. Website, detail of News section

The presentation and layout of the news page is offered considering a balance between information and usability.

5.1.6 Synergies section

The Synergies section contains any connection to other relative projects and programs. The logos of the projects will be clickable for more information.

Figure 15. Website, detail of Synergies section

5.1.7 Social network

The website is part of the dissemination strategy that considers also the use of other platforms, such as social networks. The connection with them is present all along the site, both by means of a direct access to them and the facilities to share any content in the site from any particular account.

The connection to the RAMONES social network accounts: Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, LinkedIn and YouTube, can be achieved directly through the logo of each network displayed in the top head menu and the footer. After selecting any social network, a new tab is opened in the browser with the access to its home page.

Another usage of the Social media icons is for sharing content from the website. The next picture below shows the resulting action of clicking on any icon (e.g. LinkedIn): an extra window is opened with the access to them.

Figure 16. Website, sharing content from RAMONES site to LinkedIn

5.2 Main menu

This menu offers the main contents concerning the project itself, presenting the approach of RAMONES, the Environmental Intelligence sector and any training, event and publication related to the project.

5.2.1 The Approach Section

This section presents the aim of the RAMONES project.

Design, develop and validate for the first time, a broad set of novel instruments for measuring radioactivity in seabed and water column. RAMONES will develop novel radiometry instruments specially designed as payload to a group of new submarine platforms and vehicles. The focus is on employing and integrating the new generation of detectors and sensors, offering radiation imaging capabilities near the ocean seabed.

Design, develop and validate novel adaptation, self-deployment and self-awareness collaborative marine robotics capabilities for the efficient operation and sensing with the new marine radiometry instrumentation.

Figure 17. Website, detail of Approach section

5.2.2 Environmental Intelligence

This section will include the collaborations of the project RAMONES with other H2020 pathfinder projects towards forming a blueprint for Environmental Intelligence.

RAMONES is collaborating with other H2020 Pathfinder Projects (ReSET, WachPlant, i-SEED, SmartLagoon) to shape the roadmap of Environmental Intelligence in Europe for the next decade. Through close collaboration and planned joint activities, a blueprint of emergent technologies and advanced modeling will be developed to underline the solutions needed towards a holistic approach in achieving environmental sustainability.

Figure 18. Website, detail of Environmental Intelligence section

5.2.3 Training section

This section contains held or planned webinars, summer schools, hands-on practical training and internships. They will be organised in 5 tabs for better navigation of the user. Provisionally these tabs are under construction.

Figure 19. Website, Training section details

5.2.4 Events section

This section lists any event held or planned. Brief presentation is displayed, with the option to enlarge the description and access to the whole content. There is also a search tool and a sidebar on the right part of the page for easier navigation.

Figure 20. Website, Events section details

5.2.5 Publications section

This section lists any publication produced by the project or relevant to it. There is also a search tool and a sidebar on the right part of the page for easier navigation.

Figure 21. Website, Publications section details

5.2.6 Get in touch section

This section offers another option to access the project managers for any issue concerning the project or the website itself.

Figure 22. Website, Get in touch section details

6. Social Media

Social media plays a vital role in networking and communication. These platforms are a cost-effective way to publicize and create awareness for the project. They help increase visibility, both online and offline, and recognition from the scientific community, as well as people with varying interests. Another advantage of using social media is the ability to inform the audience about our achievements simultaneously, at the exact moment something is happening. They will also help with crossing borders and reaching generations impossible to reach via a conference or science fair.

In this day and age, with over a billion sites competing for the highest ranking in search engines, it is no longer enough to optimize a website and update a blog. Search engine optimization (SEO) refers to methods used to increase traffic to a website by increasing its search engine page rank. SEO requirements are continuously varying. Therefore, sharing content on social media will help with ranking at the top of the search engines and increase validity and constancy. With the right tools and strategy, the RAMONES project will benefit from social media platforms and reach a wide audience worldwide.

The social media platforms the RAMONES project will be using are Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, LinkedIn and YouTube. The website will also host a blog, which will be updated regularly. RAMONES will be following the S.M.A.R.T. goal framework: Specific, Measurable, Attainable, Relevant, Time-bound.

RAMONES has started its online presentation on all major social media platforms. With more than 2 billion active users on Facebook, and more than 1 billion active users on Instagram, these platforms will be used to reach the maximum possible number of public audience and thematic groups related to scientific areas of RAMONES project. Twitter will be used as a news feed by RAMONES partners to keep the audience up-to-date on our daily activities, goals and achievements. Sneak peeks will also be released through Facebook and Instagram stories. Each social media platform will target different groups, e.g. LinkedIn is more career-oriented as opposed to the aforementioned. LinkedIn will be used to connect with other researchers, business organizations and research institutes relevant to RAMONES objectives and vision. Finally, RAMONES partners will use YouTube and RAMONES blog to release news, webinars, and vlogs on a bigger scale to reach a broader audience on a more long-standing time scale.

The ultimate goal will be to improve the SEO and drive maximum traffic to RAMONES website and build an engaged following for the long run.

The RAMONES partners aim to be active in an almost daily manner and limit their response rate to under one (1) hour, as well as to encourage their audience to share their content on their own social media accounts to attract more potential followers. Tracking, analyzing, and responding to conversations about RAMONES on social media via social listening, a crucial component of audience research, is also a main goal.

Vanity metrics like the number of followers and likes are easy to track, but their real value is hard to prove. Instead, focus will be brought on the engagement, click-through, and conversion rates. Social media analytics will provide valuable information about who the followers are, where they live, and how they interact with the project on social media. These insights will allow the RAMONES communication and dissemination team to evaluate, adjust and refine their strategy at the end of each month and better target RAMONES audience. Along with analytics, a monthly social media audit will be conducted, to improve the strategy and engagement rate, and to ensure EU RAMONES has no impostors mimicking its accounts and using its name.

Website, Social Media

Figure 23. Analytics for the first week since the creation of the Ramones EU Facebook page

In the meantime, RAMONES communication and dissemination team will follow relevant pages to RAMONES, in order to conduct a competitive analysis and learn from the strategies that have led to their online success. Potential synergies with innovative projects loosely or strongly related with our objectives will be explored through the social media accounts.

Finally, RAMONES communication and dissemination team will create a weekly social media content calendar to schedule all posts in advance to avoid last-minute mishaps, and to achieve simultaneous posting across social media platforms. RAMONES communication and dissemination team will strive to improve the quality of the social outlets and the content-sharing schemes.

Facebook: [Ramones EU](#)

Figure 24. The RAMONES project Facebook home page

Instagram: [ramones_eu](https://www.instagram.com/ramones_eu)

Figure 25. The RAMONES project Instagram home page

Twitter: [ramones_eu](https://twitter.com/ramones_eu)

Twitter: [ramones_eu](https://twitter.com/ramones_eu)

ramones_eu
@ramones_eu
RAMONES: RAdioactivity Monitoring in Ocean Ecosystems is an EU-H2020-FET funded project bringing radical new tech solutions for marine radioactivity studies
Joined November 2020
6 Following 22 Followers

ramones_eu Retweeted
CGIAR Platform for Big Data in Agriculture @CGIAR_Data · Jan 31
What are the #FAIRData principles & how do they impact #OpenScience? How are they assessed in #GARDIAN-- @CGIAR's flagship data harvester?
#Data experts from @IFPRI & @SCIO_systems discuss these Qs in this webinar recording: bit.ly/2Y7ORCf

WEBINAR
FAIR GUIDELINES & ASSESSMENT IN GARDIAN
The webinar will provide an introduction to the FAIR principles and their impact on Open Science.

You might like
Ευρωπαϊκή Επιτροπή... @EEAtheta
Dr. Haroon Rafique @coachrafique
Sofia @sofiaphys

Figure 26. The RAMONES project Twitter home page

Linkedin: [RAMONES EU project](#)

RAMONES EU project · 2nd

RAMONES is a new EU Pathfinder project (EU-H2020-FETPROACT) aiming to provide large-scale, continuous monitoring of radioactivity in deep ocean using autonomous gliders and a fleet of next-gen radiation instruments.

Greece · 38 connections · [Contact info](#)

Highlights

4 mutual connections
You and RAMONES both know Stefanos Pelonis, Marianthi Anastasatou, and 2 others

Activity
38 followers

- Shaping Environmental Intelligence in EU: RAMONES is a key partner in a group of...
RAMONES shared this
9 Reactions
- Improving the aspect of historic geological maps Βελτιώνοντας την...
RAMONES shared this
1 Reaction
- RAMONES is now featured on the EU news. Feel free to distribute the link t...
RAMONES shared this
3 Reactions
- Solar activity reconstructed over a millennium using radioactive carbon ...
RAMONES shared this
4 Reactions

People also viewed

- Stefanos Pelonis · 1st
BSc Candidate at the Faculty of Nuclear and Particles Physics at NKUA.
[Message](#)
- Nektarios Skamnakis · 3rd
TMIA at EEAE - Greek Atomic Energy Commission
[Message](#)
- Imata aggee · 3rd
Student at hope African university
[Connect](#)
- Anastasios Marantos · 3rd
PhD Candidate in Biocomplexity, Niels Bohr Institute
[Message](#)
- Leonidas Stravoudakis · 2nd
Production Engineer at ASML
[Connect](#)

[Show more](#)

Figure 27. The RAMONES project LinkedIn home page

YouTube: [project ramones_eu](https://www.youtube.com/projectramones_eu)

Figure 28. The RAMONES project YouTube channel home page